

Entrepreneurship Skills and Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State

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ABSTRACT

Nigerian Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) face persistent challenges in sales growth, profitability, employment creation, and employee satisfaction, partly due to inadequate entrepreneurship development and skill enhancement programmes. Despite existing support initiatives, their impact remains inconsistent. This study aimed to examine the influence of entrepreneurial skills on SME performance in Oyo State, Nigeria. The population consisted of all 7,987 SME managers operating in the state, based on data from the National Bureau of Statistics. Using the Taro Yamane formula, a sample size of 381 was determined. Purposive sampling was employed to select participants from six local government areas across the three senatorial districts, ensuring balanced geographical representation. A structured questionnaire, designed on a four-point Likert scale, was adopted as the data collection instrument. Its validity was confirmed through expert review, and reliability was established via test-retest with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.879. Data were analysed using SPSS v24, employing descriptive statistics and multiple regression to assess the impact of entrepreneurial skills on SME sustainability and performance. Results showed a positive impact on sales growth ($\bar{x} = 3.20$), indicating that entrepreneurial competencies such as innovation and market engagement enhance customer base and revenue. Profitability results ($\bar{x} = 3.12$) suggest that financial acumen and strategic decision-making significantly improve profit margins. Operational efficiency ($\bar{x} = 3.13$) was improved through better resource management and streamlined processes. Effectiveness ($\bar{x} = 3.04$) was positively influenced by optimal resource use and enhanced productivity. Strategic activities ($\bar{x} = 3.15$) were strengthened through proactive planning and market responsiveness. The findings confirmed that entrepreneurial competencies such as creativity, communication, critical thinking, and strategic planning are essential drivers of SME performance. The study concludes that entrepreneurship skills significantly enhance business sustainability, operational outcomes, and competitiveness. It recommends targeted training, mentorship, financial literacy programmes, process optimisation workshops, and strategy development support. These initiatives should be implemented to strengthen SME capacity, promote innovation, and ensure long-term growth.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial Skills, Operational Efficiency, Performance, Profitability, Strategic Activities, Sale Growth

1.0 Introduction

Performance represents the cornerstone of progress and sustainable growth in business, particularly for small and medium enterprises (SMEs). Key performance indicators such as sales growth, employment creation, profitability, and employee satisfaction collectively gauge organisational health and trajectory. When these indices improve, they signal both strategic effectiveness and capacity to thrive amid evolving market dynamics (Ibrahim & Mustapha, 2019). Despite numerous government interventions aimed at fostering SME development, underlying issues continue to hinder progress. The Nigerian Bureau of Statistics and Small and Medium Enterprise Development Agency of Nigeria (NBS/SMEDAN) study revealed that Nigerian SMEs face significant obstacles in scaling operations, including limited finance access, inadequate infrastructure, bureaucratic bottlenecks, and skilled labour shortages (Taiwo & Falohun, 2016). These challenges persist despite SMEs contributing approximately 70% of industrial employment and over 50% of Nigeria's GDP (Taiwo & Falohun, 2016; Oyedokun & Somoye, 2018c). SMEs remain highly susceptible to failure, with various factors contributing to their vulnerability: difficulty accessing credit, harsh economic conditions from unstable government policies, gross undercapitalisation, dilapidated infrastructure, high operating costs, corruption, and insufficient government support (Taiwo & Falohun, 2016; Oyedokun & Adeyemi, 2019). According to SMEDAN, 80% of SMEs struggle to operate and may cease operations within five years due to tax-related issues (Oyedokun, & Somoye, 2018a; Adanlawo & Vezi-Magigaba, 2022). The mortality rate among African SMEs remains exceptionally high, with five out of seven new businesses failing within their first year (Oyedokun, Awogbade, & Hassan, 2018; Adanlawo & Vezi-Magigaba, 2022).

Key performance indicators for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) include several essential dimensions reflecting their success and sustainability. Sales growth measures an enterprise's ability to expand revenue, attract customers, and increase market presence (Oyedokun & Somoye, 2018b; Adanlawo & Vezi-Magigaba, 2022). Sustained sales growth is vital for SMEs' financial viability, relying on entrepreneurial skills such as market research, innovation, strategic planning, and customer relationship management (Aminu & Mohd Shariff, 2015). Employment creation is critical, as SMEs reduce unemployment and promote inclusive growth by generating direct and indirect jobs through effective human resource management and workforce development (Adanlawo & Vezi-Magigaba, 2022; Oyedokun, Oyedokun, & Oyedokun, 2025). Profitability serves as a benchmark for operational efficiency and value creation, allowing SMEs to reinvest and manage market uncertainties through sound financial and cost control strategies (Oguh & Bello, 2023). Employee satisfaction influences organisational culture and productivity; supportive environments and skills development help retain talent and improve performance (Adanlawo & Vezi-Magigaba, 2022).

This study focuses on five entrepreneurial skill categories: business management, critical thinking, strategic thinking, communication, and creativity skills. These competencies underpin SME success and economic participation (Sariwulan et al., 2020). Business management skills enable navigating operations and exploiting opportunities (Negeri et al., 2023; Ibidunni et al., 2021). Critical thinking supports informed decision-making and risk assessment (Akande, 2011; Ahmad & Ahmad, 2021). Strategic thinking facilitates long-term planning and market adaptation (Obaji et al., 2020; Sedyastuti et al., 2021). Communication skills foster trust and collaboration with stakeholders (Franco & Prata, 2019; Rahim, 2020). Creativity encourages innovation and

differentiation in the marketplace (Oyedokun, 2019; Soomro & Shah, 2019; Matic, 2022). Collectively, these skills form a comprehensive framework vital for enhancing SME performance and sustainability.

Problem Statement

Nigerian SMEs face persistent challenges hindering success in sales growth, employment creation, profitability, and employee satisfaction. Inadequate entrepreneurship development support and overlooked skill enhancement programmes limit growth potential (Arinzeh, 2022). Despite various support programmes, impact remains inconsistent.

Existing studies have explored entrepreneurial skills' impact on SME performance, yet gaps exist in understanding how these skills specifically contribute to Nigerian SME performance. This study addresses this gap by utilising unique sub-variables to examine each performance metric individually and collectively, providing comprehensive understanding of factors influencing Nigerian SME success.

This research distinguishes itself by addressing Nigerian SME performance metrics through unique sub-variables tailored to each aspect. By focusing on specific entrepreneurial skill categories, the study examines nuanced factors affecting SME success. Unlike previous research often overlooking Nigerian SMEs' specific challenges, this study offers detailed examination of performance-contributing factors (Bich & Thai, 2019; Campos, 2021).

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study aims to investigate entrepreneurship skills and performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State. The specific objectives are to:

1. examine the influence of entrepreneurship skills (business management skills, critical thinking skills, strategic thinking skills, communication skills, creativity skills) on the Sales Growth of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State
2. investigate the influence of entrepreneurship skills (business management skills, critical thinking skills, strategic thinking skills, communication skills, creativity skills) on Profitability of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State
3. determine the influence of entrepreneurship skills (business management skills, critical thinking skills, strategic thinking skills, communication skills, creativity skills) on Efficiency of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State
4. determine the influence of entrepreneurship skills (business management skills, critical thinking skills, strategic thinking skills, communication skills, creativity skills) on effectiveness of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State
5. assess the influence of entrepreneurship skills (business management skills, critical thinking skills, strategic thinking skills, communication skills, creativity skills) on Strategic Activity of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State

Research Questions

1. What is the influence of entrepreneurship skills (business management skills, critical thinking skills, strategic thinking skills, communication skills, creativity skills) on the Sales Growth of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State?
2. How do entrepreneurship skills (business management skills, critical thinking skills, strategic thinking skills, communication skills, creativity skills) impact the profitability of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State?

3. What is the influence of entrepreneurship skills (business management skills, critical thinking skills, strategic thinking skills, communication skills, creativity skills) on the efficiency of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State?
4. How do entrepreneurship skills (business management skills, critical thinking skills, strategic thinking skills, communication skills, creativity skills) affect the effectiveness of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State?
5. To what extent do entrepreneurship skills (business management skills, critical thinking skills, strategic thinking skills, communication skills, creativity skills) influence the strategic activities of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State?

Hypotheses

H₀1: entrepreneurship skills (business management skills, critical thinking skills, strategic thinking skills, communication skills, creativity skills) have no significant influence on the sales growth of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State.

H₀2: entrepreneurship skills (business management skills, critical thinking skills, strategic thinking skills, communication skills, creativity skills) have no significant influence on the profitability of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State.

H₀3: entrepreneurship skills (business management skills, critical thinking skills, strategic thinking skills, communication skills, creativity skills) have no significant influence on the efficiency of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State.

H₀4: entrepreneurship skills (business management skills, critical thinking skills, strategic thinking skills, communication skills, creativity skills) have no significant influence on the effectiveness of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State.

H₀₅: entrepreneurship skills (business management skills, critical thinking skills, strategic thinking skills, communication skills, creativity skills) have no significant influence on the strategic activities of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State.

2.0 Theoretical Framework

The Resource-Based View (RBV) was formally introduced by Wernerfelt (1984) in his seminal paper, *A Resource-Based View of the Firm*. However, the foundational concepts of RBV were earlier laid out by Penrose (1959) in *The Theory of the Growth of the Firm*. Wernerfelt (1984) described RBV as a framework focusing on a firm's strategic resources, positing that these resources are crucial for gaining and sustaining competitive advantage. Building on this, Barney (1991) expanded the concept by defining resources as assets, capabilities, organisational processes, firm attributes, information, and knowledge controlled by a firm. Barney introduced the VRIN criteria, arguing that for resources to yield competitive advantage, they must be valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable. Penrose (1959) emphasised the importance of firm-specific resources and managerial capabilities in fostering firm growth and performance.

Critics argue that RBV is overly static and insufficiently accounts for the evolution of resources and capabilities in dynamic markets (Hendrawan et al., 2023). The VRIN criteria can be vague and open to interpretation, and RBV tends to focus heavily on internal resources while underestimating external factors such as market conditions and competition. Despite these critiques, RBV remains valuable in highlighting the unique internal resources and capabilities that can provide firms with a competitive edge. It encourages firms to identify, develop, and protect key resources crucial for

sustaining competitive advantage. The framework integrates resource and capability considerations into strategic planning and decision-making.

This study applies RBV to explore the relationship between entrepreneurial skills and Small and Medium Enterprise (SME) performance. Entrepreneurial skills such as digital literacy, economic literacy, and innovation are critical internal resources SMEs must cultivate to achieve superior performance. RBV facilitates understanding of how SMEs can build and sustain competitive advantage by leveraging unique capabilities. It guides SMEs in strategically utilising internal resources to adapt to market changes, improve productivity, and foster innovation, thereby enhancing overall performance.

RBV offers a robust, comprehensive framework to understand how entrepreneurial skills contribute to SME performance, addressing both tangible and intangible resources. Given the study's focus on direct and indirect effects of entrepreneurial skills, RBV's emphasis on internal capabilities is highly relevant. The theory provides strategic insights into resource management and capability development, essential for SMEs aiming to enhance competitiveness and performance in the digital era. Furthermore, the VRIN criteria offer clear guidance for evaluating and improving entrepreneurial skills, reducing reliance on supplementary theories.

In conclusion, the Resource-Based View is an appropriate and sufficient theoretical framework for investigating the impact of entrepreneurial skills on SME performance. It offers a detailed approach to understanding how internal resources and capabilities can be developed and leveraged

for competitive advantage, encompassing all critical aspects of this study without requiring additional theoretical support (Héraud, 2021; Hendrawan et al., 2023; DeKeyser, 2020).

3.0 Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive research design, which was suitable for providing a detailed and systematic representation of the phenomenon under investigation. This design allowed the researcher to quantitatively measure and describe relationships among variables without manipulating them. Primary data were collected through the administration of a structured questionnaire, while secondary data were sourced from SME records. The descriptive design further enabled the generalisation of findings from the sample to the larger population of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Oyo State, Nigeria.

The target population for the study comprised all SME managers operating within Oyo State. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), there were 7,987 SMEs in the state, consisting of 7,468 small enterprises and 519 medium enterprises. These businesses cut across different sectors and represented the economic diversity of the region. Given this manageable population size, a sample was determined using the Taro Yamane formula: $n = N / (1 + N(e)^2)$, where n represented the sample size, N the population size (7,987), and e the level of precision (0.05). The resulting sample size was approximately 381 SME managers.

A purposive sampling technique was employed to select the 381 participants. This method was appropriate for targeting SME managers in areas where such businesses were most densely concentrated. The sample was drawn from the three senatorial districts of Oyo State, with two

local government areas selected from each district. The selected areas included Oluyole and Atiba (Oyo Central), Ogbomoso South and Saki West (Oyo North), and Ibadan South West and Ibadan North (Oyo South). These locations were chosen for their high commercial activities and concentration of SMEs. The distribution of the sample across the selected local government areas ensured balanced representation and geographical spread.

The primary data collection instrument was a structured questionnaire designed on a four-point Likert scale. Respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement with a series of statements, with options ranging from 'Strongly Agree' (4 points) to 'Strongly Disagree' (1 point). This approach enabled the measurement of attitudes, opinions, and perceptions in a quantifiable format suitable for statistical analysis.

The validity of the research instrument was assessed through face and content validation. The initial draft of the questionnaire was reviewed by the researcher's academic supervisor to ensure that the items aligned with the research objectives and adequately captured the constructs under investigation. Necessary modifications were made based on the feedback received to produce a refined and valid instrument.

To establish the reliability of the instrument, the test-retest method was employed over a two-week interval. The consistency of responses across both administrations was evaluated using Cronbach's Alpha. This statistic measured the internal consistency of the items and reflected how well they collectively measured the same construct. An α -value of 0.879 was obtained, providing a basis for assessing the instrument's dependability.

The collected data were coded and analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 24. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, means, and standard deviations were used to summarise the data. Inferential analysis involved the use of multiple regression to examine the predictive influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable, which was SME survival. This provided insights into the extent to which operational environment factors contributed to the sustainability and performance of SMEs in the region.

Results and Discussion of Findings

The Results and Discussion of Findings of the investigation are presented in this chapter. The findings were based on the research questions and hypotheses that were raised in accordance with the study objective.

Analysis of Demographic Data

Table 1: demographic profile of students

Demographic Profile	Category	Frequency	Percent (%)
Age	18-24	26	6.8%
	25-34	96	25.2%
	35-44	105	27.6%
	45-54	58	15.2%
	55-64	85	22.3%
	65 Or Older	11	2.9%
Gender	Male	262	68.8%
	Female	119	31.2%
Educational background	High School or below	15	3.9%
	NCE	52	13.6%
	Bachelor's Degree	187	49.1%
	Master's Degree	123	32.3%
	Doctorate or Professional Degree	4	1.0%

Employment status	Employed Full-time	240	63.0%
	Employed part-time	76	19.9%
	Self-employed	65	17.1%

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey, 2024

The study participants include the 381 managers of all Small and Medium Enterprises (Small and Medium Enterprises) operating within Oyo State, Nigeria. 381 questionnaires were administered among the respondents. The research analyzed personal data of the respondents includes Gender: male managers are 262 representing 68.8% and female participants are 119 representing 31.2%. Regarding age distribution, the largest proportion of respondents falls within the 35-40 age group, representing 27.6% (105) of the sample. This is followed by 25-34 age group, representing 25.2% (96) of the sample, by 55-64 age group, representing 22.3% (85) of the sample, by 45-54 age group, representing 15.2% (58) of the sample, by 18-24 age group, representing 6.8% (26) of the sample. Meanwhile, 65 or older age group, representing least age group with 2.9% (11) of the sample. In terms of academic qualifications, the majority of respondents hold a Bachelor degree holders, accounting for 49.1% (187) of the sample. This is followed by Master degree holders representing 32.3% (123) of respondents, by individuals with NCE certificate holders representing at 13.6% (52) of respondents, by High School or below holder representing 3.9% (15) of respondents, and by individuals with Doctorate or Professional Degree holders representing at 1.0% (4) of respondents. When considering Employment status distribution, the data show that the majority of respondents fall under the Employed Full-time category representing 63.0% (240) of sample. This is followed by Employed part-time 19.9% (76) of respondents, while the Self-employed comprises 17.1% (65) of the respondents. The detail is in table 1.

4.2 Analysis of Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

Research question 1: What is the influence of entrepreneurship skills on the Sales Growth of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State?

Table 2: Influence of Entrepreneurship Skills on the Sales Growth of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State

Variable items	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	
1. My company's sales have increased steadily over the past 3 years.	0	0.0%	91	23.9%	127	33.3%	163	42.8%	3.19
2. I have been able to expand my customer base and gain new market share.	15	3.9%	48	12.6%	177	46.5%	141	37.0%	3.17
3. The revenue generated by my company has grown significantly in recent years.	0	0.0%	63	16.5%	160	42.0%	158	41.5%	3.25
Weighted Mean									3.20

Table 2 provides insights into respondent perceptions regarding the influence of entrepreneurship skills on the Sales Growth of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State. The data reveals a generally positive outlook on the influence of entrepreneurship skills on the Sales Growth of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State. Specifically, 42.8% of respondents strongly agreed and 33.3% of respondents agreed that their company's sales have increased steadily over the past 3 years with ($\bar{x} = 3.19$), 37.0% of respondents strongly agreed and 46.5% of respondents agreed that they have been able to expand my customer base and gain new market share with ($\bar{x} = 3.17$).

Similarly, 41.5% of respondents strongly agreed and 42.0% of respondents agreed that the revenue generated by my company has grown significantly in recent years with ($\bar{x} = 3.25$). The weighted mean score of the influence of entrepreneurship skills on the Sales Growth of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State is 3.20 ($\bar{x} = 3.20$), The weighted mean score suggested that the entrepreneurship skills have influence of on Sales Growth of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State.

Research question 2: How do entrepreneurship skills impact the profitability of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State?

Table 3: Influence of Entrepreneurship Skills on the Profitability of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State

Variable Items	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	
1. My company has maintained a healthy profit margin over the past 3 years.	18	4.7%	89	23.4%	158	41.5%	116	30.4%	2.98
2. I have been able to improve the overall profitability of my business.	0	0.0%	112	29.4%	69	18.1%	200	52.5%	3.23
3. My company's financial performance has been consistently strong.	21	5.5%	81	21.3%	97	25.5%	182	47.8%	3.15
Weighted Mean									3.12

Table 3 provides insights into respondent perceptions regarding the influence of entrepreneurship skills on the profitability of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State. The data reveals a generally positive outlook on the influence of entrepreneurship skills on the profitability of Small

and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State. Specifically, 30.4% of respondents strongly agreed and 41.5% of respondents agreed that their company has maintained a healthy profit margin over the past 3 years with ($\bar{x} = 2.98$), 52.5% of respondents strongly agreed and 18.1% of respondents agreed that they have been able to improve the overall profitability of my business with ($\bar{x} = 3.23$), Similarly, 47.8% of respondents strongly agreed and 25.5% of respondents agreed that their company's financial performance has been consistently strong with ($\bar{x} = 3.15$). The weighted mean score of the influence of entrepreneurship skills on the profitability of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State is 3.12 ($\bar{x} = 3.12$). The weighted mean score suggested that the entrepreneurship skills have influence of on the profitability of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State.

Research Question 3: What is the influence of entrepreneurship skills on the efficiency of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State?

Table 4: Influence of entrepreneurship skills on the efficiency of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State

Variable items	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	
	1. I am able to achieve my company's key objectives and goals effectively.	24	6.3%	45	11.8%	179	47.0%	133	
2. My company's operations are well-organized and streamlined.	3	0.8%	111	29.1%	158	41.5%	109	28.6%	2.98

3. I am satisfied with the overall effectiveness of my company's performance.	36	9.4%	82	21.5%	98	25.7%	165	43.3%	3.03
Weighted Mean									3.13

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

Table 4 provides insights into respondent perceptions regarding the influence of entrepreneurship skills on the efficiency of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State. The data reveals a generally positive outlook on the influence of entrepreneurship skills on the efficiency of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State. Specifically, 34.9% of respondents strongly agreed and 47.0% of respondents agreed that they are able to achieve my company's key objectives and goals effectively with ($\bar{x} = 3.11$), 28.6% of respondents strongly agreed and 41.5% of respondents agreed that their company's operations are well-organized and streamlined with ($\bar{x} = 2.98$). Similarly, 43.3% of respondents strongly agreed and 25.7% of respondents agreed that they are satisfied with the overall effectiveness of my company's performance with ($\bar{x} = 3.03$). The weighted mean score of the influence of entrepreneurship skills on the efficiency of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State is 3.13 ($\bar{x} = 3.13$). The weighted mean score suggested that entrepreneurship skills have influence of on the efficiency of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State.

Research question 4: How do entrepreneurship skills affect the effectiveness of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State

Table 5: Influence of entrepreneurship skills on the effectiveness of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State

Variable items	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	
1. My company utilizes its resources (time, money, personnel) optimally.	8	2.1%	98	25.7%	113	29.7%	162	42.5%	3.13
2. I have been able to improve the efficiency of my company's processes.	11	2.9%	117	30.7%	107	28.1%	146	38.3%	3.02
3. My company operates with minimal waste and maximum productivity.	13	3.4%	45	11.8%	160	42.0%	163	42.8%	3.24
Weighted Mean									3.04

Table 5 provides insights into respondent perceptions regarding the influence of entrepreneurship skills on the effectiveness of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State. The data reveals a generally positive outlook on the influence of entrepreneurship skills on the effectiveness of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State. Specifically, 42.5% of respondents strongly agreed and 29.7% of respondents agreed that their company utilizes its resources (time, money, personnel) optimally with ($\bar{x} = 3.13$), 38.3% of respondents strongly agreed and 28.1% of respondents agreed that they have been able to improve the efficiency of my company's processes with ($\bar{x} = 3.02$). Similarly, 42.8% of respondents strongly agreed and 42.0% of respondents agreed that their company operates with minimal waste and maximum productivity with ($\bar{x} = 3.24$). The weighted mean score of the influence of entrepreneurship skills on the effectiveness of Small and Medium

Enterprises in Oyo State is 3.04 ($\bar{x} = 3.04$). The weighted mean score suggested that entrepreneurship skills have influence of on the effectiveness of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State.

Research Question 5: To what extent do entrepreneurship skills influence the strategic activities of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State?

Table 6: Influence of entrepreneurship skills on the strategic activities of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State

Variable items	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	
I. I actively pursue new strategic initiatives to drive my company's growth.	0	0.0%	75	19.7%	161	42.3%	145	38.1%	3.18
II. My company's strategic planning has led to tangible improvements.	15	3.9%	85	22.3%	131	34.4%	150	39.4%	3.09
III. I am proactive in adapting my company's strategic activities to market changes.	0	0.0%	112	29.4%	92	24.1%	177	46.5%	3.17
weighted mean									3.15

Table 6 provides insights into respondent perceptions regarding the influence of entrepreneurship skills on the strategic activities of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State. The data reveals a generally positive outlook on the influence of entrepreneurship skills on the strategic activities of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State. Specifically, 38.1% of respondents strongly agreed and 42.3% of respondents agreed that they actively pursue new strategic initiatives to drive my

company's growth with ($\bar{x} = 3.18$), 39.4% of respondents strongly agreed and 34.4% of respondents agreed that their company's strategic planning has led to tangible improvements with ($\bar{x} = 3.09$). Similarly, 46.5% of respondents strongly agreed and 24.1% of respondents agreed that they are proactive in adapting my company's strategic activities to market changes with ($\bar{x} = 3.17$). The weighted mean score of the influence of entrepreneurship skills on the strategic activities of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State is 3.15 ($\bar{x} = 3.15$). The weighted mean score suggested that entrepreneurship skills have influence of on the strategic activities of Small and Medium Enterprises in Oyo State.

Discussion of the Findings

Entrepreneurship skills had a statistically significant and positive influence on the sales growth of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Oyo State. This finding aligns with previous research which established that entrepreneurial competencies assist SMEs in mitigating environmental pressures and fostering innovation, thereby enhancing performance (Salameh et al., 2022). Similarly, research conducted in Ghana showed that the educational qualifications of entrepreneurs and enterprise size significantly affect SME growth (Stefan, 2021). Another study confirmed that higher levels of risk-taking and innovativeness among business owners lead to improved SME performance (Kuratko, Fisher, & Audretsch, 2021).

In terms of profitability, entrepreneurship skills also had a statistically significant and positive effect. This result corroborates earlier findings that digital literacy encompassing digital business relationships, online facilities, and network capabilities exerts both direct and indirect effects on

SME performance (Chu & Luke, 2021). Entrepreneurial attributes such as risk-taking, innovation, and proactive behaviour have been shown to promote business growth and adaptability (Li et al., 2020). Likewise, entrepreneurship education, budgeting and financial literacy, and access to credit facilities were found to improve entrepreneurial performance and support poverty reduction (Negeri, Wakijira, & Kant, 2023). Further evidence revealed that entrepreneurial orientation, innovation, and competencies were significantly associated with financial, social, and environmental performance (Ibidunni, Ogundana, & Okonkwo, 2021). In addition, a moderate but positive relationship was established between cash flow practices and profitability (Akande, 2011). Entrepreneurship skills were also found to positively and significantly impact the efficiency of SMEs in Oyo State. This outcome is consistent with findings suggesting that such skills encourage SMEs to invest in growth opportunities, ultimately improving both performance and socio-economic outcomes (Ahmad & Ahmad, 2021). Other research showed that product quality, pricing, promotional strategies, and distribution networks all contribute significantly to business performance (Obaji, Olaolu, & Jumbo, 2020). Additionally, critical knowledge management practices were identified as influential factors in enhancing revenue generation and cost reduction (Sedyastuti et al., 2021).

Furthermore, entrepreneurship skills had a significant and positive effect on the effectiveness of SMEs. This finding supports previous work that highlighted how entrepreneurial competencies improve SMEs' abilities to navigate complex challenges (Franco & Prata, 2019). The implementation of technopreneurship models was also found to significantly enhance entrepreneurial development and business performance (Ekechi et al., 2024). Moreover,

entrepreneurship education was shown to strengthen competencies, eliminate barriers, and positively shape entrepreneurial intentions (Sedyastuti et al., 2021). Mentorship, too, has been acknowledged as a critical contributor to skill development and business knowledge acquisition (Yeboah, 2021). Additionally, integrating content and language learning was found to enhance entrepreneurial language proficiency while increasing motivation, self-confidence, and engagement (Franco & Prata, 2019).

Finally, entrepreneurship skills exhibited a statistically significant positive impact on the strategic activities of SMEs in Oyo State. This agrees with findings that managerial competencies positively influence SME performance, with strategic planning acting as a vital mediating factor (Rafiki, 2020). Innovativeness and proactiveness were also shown to significantly boost performance outcomes (Sedyastuti et al., 2021), while entrepreneurial competencies were observed to strengthen the direct relationship between risk-taking and performance (Ibidunni et al., 2021). Moreover, digital literacy was found to have the strongest overall influence on SME performance, both directly and indirectly (Kuratko et al., 2021). Training in customer service, opportunity identification, and record-keeping was likewise reported to contribute to SME sustainability, although high training costs remained a significant barrier (Schepers, Vandekerckhof, & Dillen, 2021).

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The findings from this study underscore the pivotal role of entrepreneurship skills in enhancing the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Oyo State, Nigeria. The results consistently revealed that entrepreneurship skills had a statistically significant and positive influence on multiple dimensions of SME performance, including sales growth, profitability, operational efficiency, effectiveness, and strategic activities. All null hypotheses were rejected, confirming the robustness of the observed relationships. The evidence indicates that competencies in creativity, communication, strategic thinking, critical thinking, and business management are vital in driving organisational success. These findings highlight the strategic importance of fostering entrepreneurship skill development among SME owners and managers as a pathway to achieving improved business outcomes and long-term sustainability. The comprehensive impact of entrepreneurial skills across various performance indicators reinforces their status as core drivers of SME success in Oyo State, with implications for similar socio-economic contexts across emerging economies.

Recommendations

In light of the findings, several practical recommendations are proposed to support SME performance through the development of entrepreneurial skills.

Firstly, stakeholders should design and implement targeted entrepreneurship training programmes that focus specifically on sales-related competencies. These should include modules on market

analysis, customer relationship management, and sales strategy development. Such training initiatives would be strengthened by mentorship schemes that connect underperforming SMEs with successful entrepreneurs who have achieved notable sales growth. Additionally, the creation of sector-specific sales toolkits would equip entrepreneurs with practical strategies for converting skills into measurable sales outcomes.

Secondly, it is recommended that entrepreneurship-focused financial literacy programmes be established to support cost management and profit margin optimisation. These initiatives should be enhanced by fostering collaborative SME networks to facilitate knowledge sharing and best practices in profitability. Introducing incentive schemes to reward innovation-led profit improvements would encourage entrepreneurs to apply their skills in financially strategic ways, thereby reinforcing the economic resilience of the SME sector in Oyo State.

Thirdly, efforts should be made to offer regular process optimisation workshops that demonstrate how entrepreneurial thinking can enhance operational efficiency. These workshops should be complemented by technology adoption initiatives that introduce cost-effective and context-appropriate digital tools for SMEs. Furthermore, the development of industry-specific benchmarking systems would allow enterprises to track improvements resulting from entrepreneurial interventions, creating a framework for continuous improvement and accountability.

Fourthly, comprehensive competency development programmes should be introduced across the region, focusing on creativity, communication, strategic thinking, and critical thinking. These

should be accompanied by the development of entrepreneurial effectiveness assessment tools to help business owners identify and address skills gaps. Establishing sector-based learning communities would further provide collaborative environments where entrepreneurs can address challenges unique to their industries and exchange practical solutions.

Finally, strategic planning workshops tailored to entrepreneurs at various stages of business development should be introduced. These should be supported by flexible decision-making frameworks that combine entrepreneurial thinking with formal business strategy methodologies. Additionally, long-term monitoring systems should be established to evaluate the impact of entrepreneurial skill development on SMEs' strategic positioning. This would guide future policy decisions and resource allocations, ensuring that investments in entrepreneurship training translate into sustainable business growth.

References

- Adanlawo, E. F., & Vezi-Magigaba, M. (2022). Exploring the impact of tax policies on small and medium scale enterprises' (SMEs) performance in Nigerian economy. *Business and Management Review*, 13(1), 1–10.
- Ahmad, I., & Ahmad, S. B. (2021). Effect of managerial skills on the performance of small- and medium-sized enterprises: A case study in Pakistan. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(4), 161–170.
- Akande, O. O. (2011). Accounting skill as a performance factor for small businesses in Nigeria. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences*, 2(5), 372–378.
- Aminu, I. M., & Mohd Shariff, M. N. (2015). Determinants of small and medium enterprises performance in Nigeria: A pilot study. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(1), 156–164.
- Arinzeh, I. F. (2022). Microcredit loan accessibility and its effect on the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria.

- Bich, N., & Thai, P. L. (2019). The effects of leadership skills on firm performance: The case of textile and garment firms in Vietnam. *Management Science Letters*, 9(12), 2121–2130.
- Campos, J. D. S. (2021). Analysis of entrepreneurial leadership skills and sustainable employee productivity of SMEs. *Journal of Social Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 1(1), 12–27.
- DeKeyser, R. (2020). Skill acquisition theory. In B. VanPatten, G. D. Keating, & S. Wulff (Eds.), *Theories in second language acquisition* (pp. 83–104). Routledge.
- Franco, M., & Prata, M. (2019). Influence of the individual characteristics and personality traits of the founder on the performance of family SMEs. *European Journal of International Management*, 13(1), 41–68.
- Hendrawan, H., Bakri, A. A., Fatchuroji, A., & Effendi, R. (2023). Effects of capital, usage of accounting information, financial statements, and entrepreneurial characteristics on financial capability and business performance of micro, small and medium enterprises. *The ES Accounting and Finance*, 1(2), 72–81.
- Héraud, J. A. (2021). A new approach of innovation: From the knowledge economy to the theory of creativity applied to territorial development. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 12(1), 201–217.
- Ibidunni, A. S., Ogundana, O. M., & Okonkwo, A. (2021). Entrepreneurial competencies and the performance of informal SMEs: The contingent role of business environment. *Journal of African Business*, 22(4), 468–490.
- Matić, I. (2022). Managerial interpersonal competencies—Benefiting from learning organisation characteristics in SMEs. *Management Dynamics in the Knowledge Economy*, 10(1), 19–36.
- Negeri, D. D., Wakijira, G. G., & Kant, S. (2023). Meta-analysis of entrepreneurial skill and entrepreneurial motivation on business performance: Mediating role of strategic leadership in SME sector of Ethiopia. *International Journal of Marketing and Digital Creative*, 1(1), 13–25.
- Obaji, O., Olaolu, D., & Jumbo, D. (2020). Entrepreneurial skills as catalyst for sustainable SME performance.

- Oguh, F. A., & Bello, U. B. (2023). Entrepreneurial business consciousness and success measures sales growth of selected SMEs in Yola South Local Government, Adamawa State. *Advance Journal of Business and Entrepreneurship Development*, 7(5), 85–106.
- Oyedokun, G. E. & Adeyemi, A.B. (2019). Human capital formation and economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Finance & Banking Studies* (2147-4486) [sbfnet.com/ojs](https://www.sbfnet.com/ojs).
- Oyedokun, G. E. & Somoye, R. O. C. (2018). Cash management and entrepreneurship growth in Nigeria. Conference Proceedings, 7th National Conference on Managing National Economic Recovery, Faculty of Administration, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Vol. 1., 141-154 July 2018
- Oyedokun, G. E. & Somoye, R. O. C. (2018a). Cash management and entrepreneurship growth in Nigeria. *Nigeria Accounting Horizon Journal (NAHJ)*. A publication of the Department of Accounting, University of Jos, Nigeria (Submitted on January 30, 2018)
- Oyedokun, G. E. & Somoye, R. O. C. (2018b). Working capital financing and entrepreneurship growth in Nigeria: An empirical investigation. A paper presented at British Academy of Management 32nd Annual Conference hosted by Bristol Business School, University of the West of England 4th - 6th September 2018
- Oyedokun, G. E. & Somoye, R. O. C. (2018c). Working capital financing and entrepreneurship growth in Nigeria: An empirical investigation. *Journal of Accounting and Finance*. 18(10), 92- 112.
- Oyedokun, G. E; Awogbade, A., & Hassan, T. A., (2018). Fiscal policy and entrepreneurship growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Science Research (IJMSR)*. A publication of Faculty of Management Sciences, University of Jos. ISSN 2536 – 605X(Print), 4(2), 119-14. Available at <https://www.ijmsr.net/index.php?journal=ijo&page=article&op=view&path%5B%5D=124&path%5B%5D=108>
- Oyedokun, G.E. (2019). *Approaches to entrepreneurship development*. Lagos, Nigeria. Aaron & Hur Publishing. ISBN: 978-978-56481-0-2
- Oyedokun, G.E., Oyedokun, D.M., & Oyedokun, P.O., (2025). Destructive Technologies, Artificial Intelligence, and the Future of Entrepreneurship in Nigeria. In A. Amodu (Eds.). Book of Readings on General Studies: Essays in Honor of Lead City University at Twenty. A publication of the Department of Politics and International Relations, Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria
- Rahim, A. R. (2020). Interpersonal skills and the impact of managerial performance through organisational commitments.
- Sariwulan, T., Suparno, S., Disman, D., Ahman, E., & Suwatno, S. (2020). Entrepreneurial performance: The role of literacy and skills. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(11), 269–280.
- Sedyastuti, K., Suwarni, E., Rahadi, D. R., & Handayani, M. A. (2021). Human resources competency at micro, small and medium enterprises in Palembang songket industry. In *2nd*

- Annual Conference on Social Science and Humanities (ANCOSH 2020)* (pp. 248–251). Atlantis Press.
- Soomro, B. A., & Shah, N. (2019). Determining the impact of entrepreneurial orientation and organizational culture on job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and employees' performance. *South Asian Journal of Business Studies*, 8(3), 266–282.
- Taiwo, J. N., & Falohun, T. O. (2016). Small and medium enterprises financing and its effects on Nigerian economic growth. *European Journal of Business, Economics and Accountancy*, 4(4), 1–10.